

Data-driven assessment of indoor climate in commercial buildings using AI-assisted control

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Abstract. Advanced HVAC control systems play a vital role in reducing energy use in commercial buildings, but ensuring indoor environmental quality (IEQ) remains essential. This paper presents a long-term, real-world evaluation of indoor climate conditions under AI-assisted HVAC control, using a commercially available and widely deployed control product. The study compares thermal comfort and indoor air quality in two actively used commercial buildings – an office and a shopping mall – before and after AI-assisted control implementation. Indoor conditions were assessed over one year using room-level sensor data and evaluated for compliance with EN 16798-1 and the Finnish Indoor Climate Classification (CIE), offering a practical benchmark rarely addressed in prior work. Results show that the AI-assisted control maintained or improved temperature and CO₂ levels relative to conventional systems, with some standard deviations attributed to occupant preferences rather than system performance. In the shopping mall, AI control achieved annual heating demand reductions of 42% and electricity savings of 22%. This study uniquely demonstrates the viability of a scaled commercial AI control system to reduce energy use while maintaining compliance with international indoor climate standards. It also underscores the value of using standardized metrics for evaluating IEQ under dynamic control strategies.

Keywords: Thermal comfort, indoor air quality (IAQ), advanced dynamic control, automated control, energy efficiency.

1 Introduction

Energy efficiency in commercial real estate is crucial for reducing both operational costs and carbon emissions. Intelligent control systems are increasingly employed to optimize energy consumption in existing commercial buildings, enabling significant energy savings while managing peak energy loads effectively through

Demand Side Management (DSM) strategies [1]–[3]. While conventional HVAC control systems typically rely on predefined schedules and static setpoints, innovative control approaches leverage artificial intelligence (AI) (machine learning (ML)) models to dynamically adjust operating parameters based on real-time indoor conditions and occupant requirements [4].

Ensuring energy efficiency while simultaneously maintaining high indoor environmental quality (IEQ) – particularly thermal comfort and indoor air quality (IAQ) – is challenging. Previous research has extensively studied advanced control algorithms but often relied primarily on simulations or short controlled tests with limited emphasis on actual measured data from buildings under real-world operational conditions and applying commercial scalable AI-assisted control [4], [5]. Long-term tests ranging from several months to years are rare (with first exceptions like [6]). Additionally, maintaining indoor climate standards compliance is essential for occupant comfort, productivity, and health. Often the comparison is done empirically and the compliance to standards is not tested.

This paper addresses these gaps by presenting a comparative, data-driven evaluation of indoor climate conditions (temperature and CO₂ levels) under conventional HVAC control versus proprietary (already scaled) AI-assisted HVAC control in two actively used commercial buildings located in Latvia and Estonia. IAQ compliance was assessed according to European standard EN 16798-1 [7] and the Finnish Classification of Indoor Climate (CIE) [8]. The primary novelty of this research is its practical demonstration of commercial AI-assisted control effectiveness using long-term measured data, evaluating not only energy savings but also maintaining or improving thermal comfort and IAQ in real-world environments.

2 Method

The methodological approach adopted in this study is summarized in the following steps:

1. Collecting one-month operational data (temperature and CO₂ levels) from buildings with conventional HVAC control.
2. After one year, collecting operational data for the same calendar month with AI-assisted HVAC control activated.
3. Analysing collected data to assess compliance with EN 16798-1 and Finnish Classification of Indoor Climate (CIE).
4. Shopping mall only: Establishing a baseline from historical energy consumption data, then comparing the baseline with the AI-assisted control period data to quantify energy savings.

Data was gathered from two commercial buildings: a shopping mall located in Latvia (64,000 m² heated floor area) and an office building in Estonia (12,000 m² heated floor area). Data on room air temperature and CO₂ concentration were collected from existing commercially available sensors integrated into the building

management system (BMS). Data was sampled at 15-minute intervals and stored over a full calendar year.

Table 1. Building parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Shopping mall	Office building
Origin country	-	Latvia	Estonia
Heated floor area	m ²	64 000	12 000
Nr of temperature sensors for offices	pcs	23	220
Nr of CO ₂ sensors	pcs	30	42
Nr of temperature sensors for retail areas	pcs	11	-

Sensor placement was determined by project engineers according to typical building operational practices. Specifically, temperature sensors were positioned in zones with local heating or cooling actuation, which include offices, meeting rooms and retail spaces, public areas in the shopping mall were heating and cooled by ventilation air. In the shopping mall, 30 CO₂ sensors were installed – 7 in public shopping areas and 23 in the office areas. In the office building, 42 CO₂ sensors were predominantly located in high occupancy areas such as meeting rooms, reflecting standard practice for offices. The main parameters of the buildings as well as number of sensors in rooms of distinct types are shown in Table 1.

Initially, buildings operated for one month under conventional, non-adaptive control (business-as-usual scenario). After this month, AI-assisted HVAC control was implemented for one year.

The AI-assisted control system, which was a commercial software product from R8 Technologies, actively adjusted operational setpoints and parameters based on occupancy, internal loads, electricity price, and external weather conditions. In the shopping mall, AI-assisted control adjusted room temperature setpoints dynamically. Additionally, it actively controlled ventilation supply air temperature, ventilation fan speeds, heating system supply water temperature, and other setpoints also adaptable by human technician. The office building employed similar AI-assisted control strategies but without direct manipulation of room-level temperature setpoints. New setpoint values were written to BMS every 15 min if needed.

Compliance of indoor climate (temperature and CO₂ concentration) was assessed according to standards EN 16798-1 and Finnish Classification of Indoor Climate (CIE). Given distinct EN-standard requirements for different room types (retail and office), these were analyzed separately to ensure relevant compliance assessments. At outdoor temperatures below 12 °C, EN 16798-1 defines class 1 for retail spaces between 17.5 and 20.5 °C, and for office spaces between 21 and 23 °C. As there is one month of data available before the control change, the comparison was based on one month a year apart. Therefore, the shopping mall results are shown for April 2022 and 2023 and office building results are shown for January 2022 and 2023. Some deviation to optimal indoor climate according to standards is expected as the building users can change the setpoints to any values.

Energy demand comparisons were carried out only for the shopping mall due to available historical data. The comparison employed weather normalization using degree-days from BizEE Degree Days data [9], following the methodology described by Kuivjõgi et al. [10]. Baseline energy consumption was computed from historical monthly data, normalized against external temperature fluctuations. Energy savings under AI-assisted control were quantified by comparing actual normalized energy demand during AI-assisted control with the baseline.

3 Results

3.1 Room air temperature

Compliance with EN 16 798-1. The temperatures in the retail areas of the shopping mall are reviewed first. The temperature distribution in April 2022 in the zones is shown in Fig. 1a together with the EN-standard comfort limits for the indoor climate classes 1 to 3. Altogether, ca 2000 *h* of data is shown in the graph. 7 of 11 assessed rooms seem to have problems following the European EN 16798-1:2019 standard's thermal comfort recommended limits. 97 % of the violations happen above the optimal temperature range, indicating that these rooms were too warm according to the standard. This indicates discrepancy between the standard's classification criteria and the wished temperatures in rooms (setpoints) or controllability of the temperatures. Even at setpoint 23 °C the variability ranges to significantly higher values.

In Fig. 1b, the temperature distribution is shown in the same rooms a year later, with advanced control. Here, the setpoint range has been set in shopping areas to range between 18 °C and 22.5 °C at outdoor temperature 5 °C and between 20.5 °C and 24 °C at outdoor temperature 15 °C. There is a linear change of limits set in between 5 °C and 15 °C outside. The desired ranges have been followed in tendency, although during rarer occasions (lighter green areas) the variance has been larger. According to the EN standard, the number of rooms in climate class 4 has reduced to 5 and it is clear that time in classes 1 and 2 have increased. Although, according to the standard the rooms are still mostly too warm.

In office areas in the shopping mall, the setpoints have been more like the standard resulting in no rooms in climate class 4. The initial temperature in the rooms ranges from 20 to 25 °C (see Fig. 1c). With advance control, the setpoints were 20-22 °C at 5 °C and 21.5- 23.5 °C at 15 °C outside with linear change of limits in between (Fig. 1d). Again, these changing limits can be detected. At rare occasions, at colder outside temperatures the temperature variance was larger than before but time in climate class 1 significantly increased.

In the office building, the thermal comfort of assessed rooms followed the European EN 16798-1:2019 standard's recommendations well both before (Fig. 2a) and with (Fig. 2b) AI-assisted control. However, ca 5 % of the rooms shifted from classes 1 and 2 to classes 3 and 4 due to higher temperature variances.

Fig. 1. Indoor climate comparison in the shopping mall according to the EN standard comparing conventional control (subfigures a and c) to AI-assisted control (b and d) in different room types (a and b retail, c and d office).

Fig. 2. Indoor climate comparison in the office building according to the EN and CIE standards comparing conventional control (a) to AI-assisted control (b)

Compliance with CIE. When evaluated against Finnish CIE standards (see also on Fig. 2), 57% of rooms in the office building were initially warmer than the recommended S1 and S2 comfort classes under conventional control. However, this may still be satisfactory if the guidelines from the local health protection act and building code requirements are met. With AI-assisted control, the compliance level showed no significant improvement or deterioration, indicating that the AI system maintained the indoor climate consistently at previous levels.

3.2 Air quality

The CO₂ concentration measurements clearly indicate robust compliance with both EN 16798-1 and CIE standards across both buildings. For the Latvian shopping mall, only one room was classified within EN 16798-1 class 3, while all others were within classes 1 and 2 under both control scenarios. In the Estonian office building, all rooms consistently remained within the optimal classes 1 and 2, demonstrating effective control of indoor air quality.

Detailed analysis of CO₂ concentration graphs revealed no significant adverse variations between conventional and AI-assisted control scenarios, confirming that the implemented AI strategies effectively maintained or slightly enhanced air quality conditions without negative impacts.

3.3 Energy demand reduction

The annual demand reduction in the shopping mall was 42% for heating and for electricity 22%. Monthly demand reductions for electricity varied from 3% (only on one month, other months above 20%) up to 47%. Monthly heating demand reductions varied from 29% to 64%, except for June-August when heating was switched off. In the month when indoor climate was compared (April 2023), the

energy demand was reduced by 64% for heating and by 32% for electricity, demonstrating the substantial energy-saving capability of AI-assisted HVAC control. No comparative energy analysis was possible for the office building due to the absence of historical baseline data.

4 Conclusions

This study demonstrates the significant potential of AI-based HVAC control systems in commercial buildings to enhance energy efficiency while maintaining indoor thermal comfort and air quality. The implementation of advanced control strategies resulted in substantial energy savings, with monthly heating demand reductions of up to 64% and electricity savings of up to 47% in the shopping mall, concluding in annual savings of 42% for heating and 22% for electricity. The indoor climate, assessed according to EN 16798-1 and Finnish CIE standards, showed improvements or comparable levels in temperature regulation and CO₂ concentrations. Although, deviations from standard comfort requirements were observed, these were expected due to differences between occupant-preferred setpoints and the standardized temperatures. These results confirm the value of integrating AI-based control strategies in commercial buildings to achieve significant energy savings without compromising indoor comfort or air quality.

References

1. C. Zhang and Z. Tan, "Entropy-driven deep reinforcement learning for HVAC system optimization," *J. Renew. Sustain. Energy*, vol. 17, no. 1, p. 015101, Jan. 2025, doi: 10.1063/5.0238799.
2. D. Lee and L. Chen, "Sustainable Air-Conditioning Systems Enabled by Artificial Intelligence: Research Status, Enterprise Patent Analysis, and Future Prospects," *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 12, p. 7514, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.3390/su14127514.
3. R. Heidarykiany and C. Ababei, "HVAC energy cost minimization in smart grids: A cloud-based demand side management approach with game theory optimization and deep learning," *Energy AI*, vol. 16, p. 100362, May 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.egyai.2024.100362.
4. J. Ogundiran, E. Asadi, and M. Gameiro Da Silva, "A Systematic Review on the Use of AI for Energy Efficiency and Indoor Environmental Quality in Buildings," *Sustainability*, vol. 16, no. 9, p. 3627, Apr. 2024, doi: 10.3390/su16093627.
5. E. Saloux, K. Zhang, and J. A. Candanedo, "A Critical Perspective on Current Research Trends in Building Operation: Pressing Challenges and Promising Opportunities," *Buildings*, vol. 13, no. 10, p. 2566, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.3390/buildings13102566.
6. M. Kong, B. Dong, R. Zhang, and Z. O'Neill, "HVAC energy savings, thermal comfort and air quality for occupant-centric control through a side-by-side experimental study," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 306, p. 117987, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.117987.

7. EN 16798-1:2019 - *Energy performance of buildings - Ventilation for buildings - Part 1: Indoor environmental input parameters for design and assessment of energy performance of buildings addressing indoor air quality, thermal environment, lighting and acoustics*. 2019.
8. Finnish Society of Indoor Air Quality and Climate, FISIAQ, The Building Information Foundation RTS sr, Helsinki, Finland, *Classification for Indoor Environment 2018*.
9. “BizEE Degree Days Homepage.” <https://www.degreedays.net/>
10. H. Kuivjõgi, S. Vasman, E. Petlenkov, M. Thalfeldt, and J. Kurnitski, “Data-driven baseline generation for post-retrofit energy saving assessment, a comparison of statistical and machine learning methods,” *J. Build. Eng.*, vol. 98, p. 111016, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.job.2024.111016.

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